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important part in the variation of interfacial tension. While for benzene and toluene having 6 and 7 carbon atoms, respectively with hydrogen and no hydrogen atom, the value is again very high. In case of crude petroleum which is a mixture of relatively higher hydrocarbons the type of surfactants mentioned above may act as efficient emulsifiers for enhanced oil recovery.

Table 2 depicts the interfacial tension of varying concentrations of surfactants against benzene. By plotting the data, it has been observed that as the concentration of surfactants increases, the interfacial tension decreases sharply and the change becomes linear at 2% of the surfactant solution.

Tables 3 and 4 present the data of salt tolerance of the surfactants. It is concluded from the data that surfactant solution/benzene interfacial tension first shows a lowering, but beyond a particular concentration of the salt the tension starts increasing. The optimum concentration of the salts to these surfactants and interfacial tension data depicts that K_2CO_3 favours maximum lowering of interfacial tension while $K_2C_2O_4$ the least. This may be due to the fact that interfacial packing of the absorbed monomers increases in presence of electrolytes causing a reduction in the electrostatic repulsive forces between the charged heads in the aqueous phase adjacent to the interface. The experimental results are in good agreement with the earlier work¹⁷.

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Studies of Turpentine/Water Emulsions Stabilized by Binary Mixtures of Indian Gums and Rosin

P. K. SHARMA and T. C. SHARMA*

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. (P.G.) College,
Dehra Dun-248 195

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OIL/WATER emulsions have been prepared by employing surfactants¹⁻³, gums^{4,5}, rosin soaps⁶ and finely divided solids⁷. Their physical properties i.e., stability⁸, demulsification⁹, interfacial tension¹⁰, effect of salinity on interfacial tension¹¹, viscosity¹², particle size distribution¹³, phase inversion¹⁴ and conductance¹⁵ have been cited in the literature. But no attempt has yet been made to prepare turpentine/water emulsions, by using mixtures of rosin and Indian gums as emulsifiers, which have great importance in paint industry. In view of this, it was thought worthwhile to undertake a systematic study of physical properties of turpentine/water emulsions stabilized by rosin-gum mixtures and to evaluate their relative emulsifier efficiency.

Experimental

Double distilled water (conductance 1×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and turpentine (sp. gr. 0.8745) were used in all the experiments. The rosin used was of grade WG 1320-21, provided by Rosin and Turpentine Factory, Tilwara, Garhwal. The gums used were *Khair* (*Acacia catechu*), *Sahjan* (*Moringa pterygosperma*), *Ghatty* (*Anogeissus latifolia*), *Karaya* (*Sterulia ureus*) and *Modal* (*Lannea grandis*) and were provided by the Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun. They were purified by the method of Ingle and Bhide¹⁶. Three sets of emulsions, as described below, were prepared by agent-in-water method¹⁷, using turpentine as the internal and water as the external phase.

1. The oil phase containing 0.5% rosin added to 0.5% aqueous solution of various gums viz., *Khair*, *Ghatty*, *Sahjan*, *Karaya* and *Modal*, respectively, keeping the oil/water ratio 1 : 3.
2. The oil phase containing 0.5% rosin and the aqueous phase having 0.5% *Khair* gum mixed in different phase volume ratio viz., 1 : 9, 2 : 8, 3 : 7, 4 : 6 and 5 : 5, respectively, the samples being homogenized by Redimix mixer.

TABLE 1.
Emulsion type O/W ; O/W Ratio 1 : 3 ; Turpentine 10 ml ; Rosin 0.5% ; Indian gums 0.5%.

Sl. No.	Gum	Viscosity (CP)	Surface tension dynes/cm $\times 10^{-3}$	Conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Particle size (μ)	Interfacial tension dynes/cm
1.	<i>Khair</i>	9.84	35.210	8.5	6-7	26.14
2.	<i>Ghatty</i>	9.50	36.40	8.2	5-7	26.92
3.	<i>Sahjan</i>	9.12	37.86	7.6	5-7	27.74
4.	<i>Karaya</i>	8.95	37.62	7.3	4-6	28.65
5.	<i>Modal</i>	8.62	38.15	6.9	4-6	29.46

3. The oil phase containing 0.5% rosin and the aqueous phase containing different concentrations viz., 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0% of *Khair* gum mixed by keeping the oil/water ratio 1 : 3.

Emulsion type (O/W or W/O) was determined by dye solubility method¹⁸. Particle size was measured by Hymoptik microscope (Occ. 10X ; Obj. 45X). Viscosity, surface tension, specific gravity and conductance were measured by Ostwald viscometer, drop weight method, pycnometer and conductance meter (WTW, German), respectively. The interfacial tension was measured by drop volume method^{19,20} from the equation :

$$Y^{\circ-w} = \frac{V(dw - d_o)g}{2\pi r f(r/v^{1/3})}$$

where $Y^{\circ-w}$ is the interfacial tension, V the volume of a single drop, d_w and d_o the densities of water and oil respectively, r the radius of the dropping tip, g the gravity and $f(r/v^{1/3})$ the correction factor. All the experiments were carried out at $20 \pm 1^\circ$. Results for the three sets of emulsions as prepared above are summarized in Tables 1-3.

TABLE 2.

Emulsion type O/W ; Rosin 0.5% ; *Khair* gum 0.5%.

Sl. No.	Phase volume ratio	Viscosity (CP)	Surface tension dynes/cm $\times 10^{-3}$	Conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Particle size (μ)
1.	1 : 9	8.93	35.43	8.0	2-4
2.	2 : 8	9.65	34.92	8.4	3-5
3.	3 : 7	10.12	32.65	9.2	4-7
4.	4 : 6	10.75	30.14	9.8	5-9
5.	5 : 5	11.24	29.10	10.3	6-9

TABLE 3.

Emulsion type ; O/W Ratio 1 : 3 ; Turpentine 10 ml ; Rosin 0.5%.

Sl. No.	<i>Khair</i> gum concn.	Viscosity (CP)	Surface tension dynes/cm $\times 10^{-3}$	Conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Particle size (μ)
1.	0.1	9.10	49.28	6.8	1-3
2.	0.2	9.25	47.42	7.3	1-3
3.	0.4	9.63	45.25	7.5	2.5-5
4.	0.6	9.84	39.14	7.9	6-8
5.	0.8	10.05	36.63	8.4	6-7
6.	1.0	10.31	33.12	8.6	6-11

Results and Discussion

Table 1 makes it clear that the viscosity, conductance and particle size values of the emulsions

are in the order *Khair* < *Ghatty* < *Sahjan* < *Karaya* < *Modal* gum, while the surface tension and interfacial tension show a reverse order. It was found that a decrease in surface tension and interfacial tension confers greater stability to the emulsions²¹. Neogy and Ghosh^{22,23} reported that higher viscosity aids the stability by decreasing the mobility of the droplets constituting the dispersed phase. The higher conductance and particle size make the emulsions coarser and favour stability.

Table 2 represents the effect of phase-volume ratio on the stability of emulsions prepared by using rosin and *Khair* gum. The increase in viscosity, conductance and particle size points to enhanced stability as the phase volume ratio is increased.

The effect of variation of *Khair* gum concentration in the mixture is shown in Table 3. The data indicate that the stability of the emulsions increases as the concentration increases.

The experimental data, therefore, indicate that *Khair* gum-rosin mixture emulsions are the most stable.

The conditions for stability of the above emulsions may find industrial application in the preparation of paints and varnishes.

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Application of Phase Transfer Catalysis in the Synthesis of Flavonoids. Part-I : Alkylation of Some Phenols**

SWADHIN NATH, ANJAN BHATTACHARYYA[†]

and

P. K. SENGUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235

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A new technique, commonly referred to as phase transfer catalysis or extractive alkylation, has come into prominence in recent years. Its application has been pioneered by the research groups of Makosza, Brandstrom and Stark^{1,2}. This new technique has been applied in various fields of organic synthesis.

In connection with the synthesis of flavonoids, we become interested in applying the phase transfer catalysis technique on the alkylation of various phenols, phenolic aldehydes, hydroxyacetophenones and phenolic acids which are common starting materials in this area of synthesis. Moreover, the flavonoids so far reported from plant sources are derived mainly from pyrogallol, resorcinol, phloroglucinol and different phenolic aldehydes or acids. Methylation and benzylation of phenolic hydroxyl groups are common procedures in the synthesis of flavonoids. In view of these, we undertook the studies on the alkylation of various phenols by using phase transfer catalysis technique. The results of this study are the subject matter of the present communication.

Recently, McKillop *et al*³ have reported a simple, rapid and efficient procedure for the monoalkylation of both simple and highly hindered phenols by using phase transfer catalysis technique. In

majority of the cases they obtained higher yields as compared to the classical methods.

McKillop's work³ in this area is mainly confined in the monoalkylation of phenols. Since the present study is related with flavonoid synthesis, so our main approach in this study is the polyalkylation of different phenols. The compounds selected for alkylation are essential starting materials for the synthesis of flavonoids. The results of such polyalkylation are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—o-ALKYLATION OF POLYHYDROXYPHENOLS AND PHENOLIC ALDEHYDES*

Compound	Alkylating agent	Yield %
1. Pyrogallol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
	PhCH ₂ Cl	40
2. Phloroglucinol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
3. Resorcinol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
4. Pyrocatechol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
5. Vanillin	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	75
	PhCH ₂ Cl	70
6. o-Vanillin	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	75
	PhCH ₂ Cl	45
7. 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	75
	PhCH ₂ Cl	40

* All the alkylated products gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

TABLE 2—o-ALKYLATION OF POLYHYDROXYACETOPHENONES AND PHENOLIC ACIDS*

Compound	Alkylating agent	Yield %
1. 2,4-Dihydroxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	PhCH ₂ Cl	40
2. 2-Hydroxy-4-benzoyloxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
3. 2,4,6-Trihydroxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
4. 2,3,4-Trihydroxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
5. Gallic acid	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
6. 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
7. Methyl ester of syringic acid	PhCH ₂ Cl	70

* All the alkylated products gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

It is evident from the present study that the yields of methylated products are extremely high in comparison to the conventional procedure. In case of benzylation, the yields of the product are comparable to the conventional methods but the benzylation product prepared by the phase transfer technique required less time and easy work-up procedure. So, the application of phase transfer catalysis technique on the polyalkylation of phenols could overcome the different drawbacks of the conventional alkylation methods and alkylation could be done more suitably. Further work in this area is in progress.

Experimental

The following general procedure have been followed.

(i) *Monoalkylation*: A method similar to the one cited in literature³ has been followed.

[†] Department of Agrl. Chemistry, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235.

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